

2015

***Electronic
International
Interdisciplinary
Research Journal
(EIIRJ)***

**REVIEWED INTERNATIONAL
JOURNAL** **VOL IV Issues I**

**Chief-Editor
Mr.Ubale Amol Baban**

www.aarhat.com
25/2/2015

**STUDY OF ATTITUDE TOWARDS ART IN RELATION TO CREATIVITY OF
SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS*****Research paper in Education******Dr. Mandeep Kaur****Assistant Professor, Khalsa College of Education, Ranjit Avenue, Amritsar****Ms. Rajwinder Kaur,****M.Ed. Student, Khalsa College of Education, Ranjit Avenue, Amritsar****Abstract**

The purpose of the present study is to investigate the relationship between attitude towards art and creativity of secondary school students of Amritsar city. The present study also examined the gender differences with respect to attitude towards art and creativity among secondary school students. For this, 200 respondents from Amritsar city of Punjab state were selected. The results of the investigation revealed that there is significant gender difference in boys and girls with respect to attitude towards art. The study further revealed that there are no gender differences in creativity. However no relationship between attitude towards art and creativity of secondary school students is found.

Keywords: *Attitude towards art, creativity, gender*

Theoretical Background

From the dawn of civilization men and women have been enjoying the virtues of music, dance and the visual arts to satisfy their urges and express their joys and sorrow. They used these performing arts to transmit the heritage of their ancestors. These arts are the means by which

civilization can be measured. Out of these performing arts, art is an essential part of human experience which plays an important role in his life. Art as creation of beauty gives us pleasure. It is a medium through which he can express his own impression, expression, feelings and emotions. Art is not a handicraft, it is transmission of feelings the artist has experienced (Tolstoy). Art is not only teaching or form of beauty, not only the discovery or the expression of beauty it is a self expression of consciousness under the condition of aesthetic vision and a perfect execution. Art is discovery and revelation of beauty, and we can say nothing more by way of prohibitive or limiting rule (Aurobindo).

We all like beauty in nature and are grateful to the artists who have preserved it in their works. It is a natural preference of most people that they like to see in pictures what they would also like to see in life reality. It is because all of us has hidden artist in ourself. Some of us have been able to found this active artist while in others the hidden art talent remains the passive. In childhood stage, every child has an artistic bent of mind. Quite early in his life, he manifests the aptitude when he starts forming, deforming and reform the houses with his imagination and the process goes on as long as the artistic urge lasts. Art it can be skillful execution as an object in itself or skill applied to imitation and design as against, fine Arts in which mind and imagination are chiefly concerned (The Oxford Dictionary). As he is unknown to drawing so he often draws lives on dust or sand as his fancy directs and manifests his inherent artistic talent. And later in school, he begins to scribble a lot with chalk and slate or pencil and paper. The young artist is drawing something in his own little way with a little goading and guidance he can soon learn to draw egg, bird, fist, cat, rat, dog boy etc.

As art is seen as necessary element for the development of the child's personality so it has been added as a subject of the school curriculum. The objective of art education is not only to train the hands for making attractive objects rather aims at the holistic development of the child. Art education aims at providing activities for continuous self expression and for constant self realization for experiment with a diversity of material and for experiences of beautiful things for recreation and for option, for mental and spiritual growth for the training of the power of observation, and lastly but by no means to be forgotten for application of the rise and fall of the sun. Imparting art education in school is not important rather teachers should develop child's attitude towards art and encourage to develop more artistic bent of mind. As art is required by

the child at all levels of education and in all subjects, positive attitude towards art is essential. Students having attitude towards are more artist than those who do not have this attitude. Students having more attitude towards art can convict their feelings by creating different objects.

Many factors such as environmental, curriculum related and administrative factors determine the attitude towards art. Beside these factors, individual factors such as personality, intecull ability, creativity, aptitude, interest etc. also play important role in developing attitude towards art. Out of these factors, creativity helps a child to see the different prospective of an object. Creativity is the ability is see things is a new and usual light, to see problems that no one else may even realize exist, and then to come up with new, unusual, and effective solutions (Paplia and Olds, 1987).

Every child is a unique creation possessing different creative abilities. Some of them are endowed with high creative talents and contributes to advancement in the fields of art, literature, science, business, teaching and other spheres of human activity and are responsible for propounding new ideas and incorporating in the society for the development of the nation. Creativity and achievement in art and painting are found to be positively and significantly correlated (Kaur, 2011). Gakhar and Sood, 2003 found creativity to be positively significant with math's achievement. Highly modern students were found to be more creative (Menon, 1980). Good education, proper care and provision of opportunities for creative expression inspire, stimulate and sharpen the creative mind, and it is in this sphere, that parents, society and teachers make a significant contribution. However, Tiwari and Sharma, 1976 found that that boys and girls to do not show any significant difference in respect of any of the three components of creative thinking namely fluency, flexibility and originality.

From the above discussion it is clear that not many researchers have examined the relationship between attitude towards art and creativity. So investigator tried to find out the relationship between attitude towards art and creativity and gender differences on measured variables.

Methodology

Research Design

The quantitative approach is applied in this study.

Respondents

Respondents were 200 respondents (100 boys and 100 girls) from Amritsar city of Punjab state.

Instruments

The following Instruments were used to collect the data for the present study:

1. Attitude towards Art Scale, 2012 (developed by investigator)
2. Non Verbal test of creative thinking by Mehdi, 1997

Description of Attitude towards Art Scale

To study the attitude towards art of secondary school students the investigator devised a suitable and appropriate attitude scale. Following steps were used in construction of scale:

1. Preparation of preliminary draft of scale

In order to construct attitude towards art investigator consulted books of research in education and critically analyzed all the available attitude scale. After a thorough study the investigator constructed Attitude towards Art scale which included 50 items.

2. Try Out

For the try out purpose, the preliminary draft of the scale was given to 10 teachers of different schools of Amritsar city. This was conducted to see the relevance of items and to note the language difficulties if any faced by the teachers in attempting the items. 36 Items were taken and 14 items were dropped.

3. Preparation of Final Draft of Scale

After incorporating the suggestions of the teachers, investigator prepared the final draft of scale. Instructions of scale were given at the cover page. Final draft consisting of 36 items. There are five options for each statement. It measures the respondents opinion on the basis of responses given as strongly Agree, Agree, Not Sure, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. There are 24 Positive Items and 11 Negative Items.

Every Positive Items response carries 5 marks for strongly agree, 4 for agree, 3 for not sure, 2 for disagree and 1 for strongly disagree. Similarly for all negative item responses scoring has been reversed. 5 marks for strongly disagree, 4 for disagree, 3 for

not sure, 2 for agree and t for strongly agree. There are 5 marks for every right answer and 1 mark for negative answer.

Data Analyses

1. Descriptive statistics like mean and SD were use to analyse the data.
2. 't' test was applied to find out the significant difference between means scores of boys and girls for variables- Creativity and Attitude Towards Art.
3. 'r' was calculated by using Pearson's Product moment coefficient of correlation method to find out the relationship between Attitude towards Art and Creativity.

Results and Interpretations:

Comparison of Mean

The results in table 1, displays the gender differences in scores on the variables of attitude towards art and creativity of secondary school boys and girls.

Table 1: Showing difference in the mean score of attitude towards art and creativity of secondary school boys and girls

Variables	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value
Attitude towards Art	Boys	100	36.79	15.675	3.30*
	Girls	100	43.81	14.367	
Creativity	Boys	100	47.82	56.041	0.34
	Girls	100	50.38	18.209	

* Significant at 0.01 level of confidence.

Table 1 reveals that the mean score of attitude towards art of boys is 36.79 and S.D is 15.675 and the mean score of attitude towards art of girls is 43.81 and S.D is 14.36. 't' value between boys and girls is found to be 3.30 which is significant at 0.01 level of confidence. It means that there is significant difference in the attitude towards art of secondary school boys and girls. From the table 1 it is clear that mean score of attitude towards art of girls is higher (m=43.81) than the boys (m= 36.79). It means that

girls have more attitude towards art than boys. The probable reason for this result is that girls have more aesthetic values than boys. They have more artistic bent of mind. They make use of effective domain more than boys.

Table 1 further reveals that the mean scores of creativity of secondary school boys is 47.82 and S.D is 56.04 and the mean score of creativity of secondary school girls is 50.38 and S.D is 18.209. 't' value between variables is .43 which is insignificant. It means that there is no significant difference in the mean score of creativity of secondary school boys and girls. The result is supported by the founding e.g. Tiwari and Sharma (1976) and Paltsingh (2010).

Correlational Analysis

Table 2 displays the results of the Pearson Product Moment Correlation between attitude towards art and creativity.

Table 2: Relationship between attitude towards art and creativity.

Variables	N	Correlation value of 'r'
Attitude towards Art Creativity	200	-.012

The data reveals no relationship correlation between attitude towards art and creativity. It means that it is not necessary that the child who has creative ability will have more attitude towards art. Number of factors are there as mentioned above that create and enhance attitude towards art.

CONCLUSION

From the above results, the following conclusions are drawn.

1. There is significant difference in the attitude towards art of Secondary School boys and girls.
2. There is no significant difference in creativity of secondary school boys and girls.
3. There is no significant relationship between attitude towards art and creativity of secondary school boys and girls.

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